

Influence of Career Development on organizational Productivity of Savings and Credit Co-Operative Societies in Kericho County

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Abstract: The aim of the study was to examine the influence of career development on organizational productivity of savings and credit co-operative societies in Kericho County. This research was useful in designing policies, practices and procedures and building strategies for employee engagement for greater success in achieving strategic business goals and high productivity. This research was focused on the theory of self-determination. Descriptive research design was employed in the analysis. Via stratified and simple random sampling methods, a target population of 600 employees and a sample of 180 were chosen. Closed and open ended questionnaires, self-administered, were used to collect primary data. From different publications, secondary data was collected. We used descriptive and inferential statistics. The data was then displayed using tables and charts of frequency distribution. Descriptive statistics was deployed including the mean and standard deviation. Inferential statistics was used for analysis. Findings established that career development had a positive significant relationship with organization productivity. This implies that career development has a positive influence on organization productivity that is significant at 5% levels of significance. The study concluded that organization should development good reviewable compensation packages, rewards and offer career development based rewards through promotion, seminars and capacity building. It recommended that organization has duty to ensure that good environment and better training to will ensure career development.

Keywords: Career Development, Kericho County, Organizational Productivity, SACCOs

I. Introduction

Retaining of employees refers to practices and policies input to encourage workers to continue in their works for a maximum duration of time. Employees are valued resources if retained in an organization they contribute positively to meeting organizational goals and objectives. This study seeks to define the benefits of putting up measures, policies and practices that enhances employee retention. It will examine the influence of the retention strategies of organizational employees on the efficiency of the company. The needs and expectations of workers today have grown exponentially every day. Their expectations are much as of their salary resulting to increase in employee turnover. According to Right Management, it expensive by thrice the wages or salary of the worker in replacing based on lost opportunity, lost productivity, severance and recruitment. Therefore, employee retention is an important aspect in each firm. [1], since it encourages current workers to stay within the company. Retaining employees is making work more efficient and effective leading to better performance of the organization. On the other hand, the labor market is growing and increasingly evolving, and the company should also respond to these changes in order to make the organization sustainable. In order to implement this, retention of workers is vital in the organization as they are the ones who push the business ahead. [2], states that organizations are confronted with people leaving to join different organizations. Over the globe, the apparent need of commitment by potential workers to employers thus allows businesses to improve productivity by better managing talent. Its worrying growth, particularly when faced by the troublesome real factors that representatives in an association have been the esteemed resources and by leaving the association could carry critical impact to association goals, hence low productivity. Their retention within the organization will contribute positively in the long term growth and success of the company and furthermore improving organization productivity. It starts with selecting and recruiting the employees with running the programs that will keep committed to the organization and maintaining acceptable relationships between them and the executives. Worker readiness upgrades their abilities, permitting them to prevail in their obligations. Vocation development prompts singular development, which expands their confidence, particularly when an organization energizes profession advancement programs.

Remuneration incorporates monetary awarded to someone as a compensation of loss or injury received by an employee from an employer as salary or wage. It can be direct or indirect rewards and benefits the employee is given on merit of performing highly in the organization. Compensation and reward program should be developed according to ability and performance of employees to the organization. This type of programs is expected to affect positively on retention and commitment of employee, hence ensures sustainability of the organization. Job satisfaction is also can be seen as one of the elements that influence one's experience or quality of task done by employee in the organization. Job satisfaction is can then be identified with working conditions, home- work balance, control at work, stress at work and general well-being of employee. "Representatives turnover is a quiet however huge benefit executioner" [3] yet workers' maintenance has a great deal of advantages. Worker proficiency, [4], alludes to the jobs and exercises that representatives perform productively and successfully. As per [5] representative execution is an action or action that can be observed to illustrate how an occupation is supposed to be conducted and to indicate the desired outcomes for a successful job performance. The paybacks a company has to give have an immense effect on the efficiency and happiness of an employee. Good employee output is the outcome of the overall quality and effectiveness of the processes of a company. Factors such as preparation, benefits, career growth and work satisfaction influence the performance of an employee. Therefore, their efficiency is profoundly influenced by the practices that organizations use to manage workers.

It is necessary to remember that one success measure should not be taken all alone. All things being equal, a thorough audit of an organization's outcomes should consider a few unique measures. Performance is described by [1] as a measurement method which assist in decision making and through this actions are taken by the organization so as to ensure effectiveness and efficiency of the past task by dissemination, interpreting, sorting, analyzing and collecting of relevant data. Firms do measure performance so as to identify the positive, benchmark or compare positions. Performance needs to be communicated to the relevant stakeholder either through internal or external mechanism so as to control expenses, investment, task or know the organizational progress. It is essential to assess corporate monetary execution measurements to assist investors and financial specialists, according to [6]. The company executive focuses on how the benefit of shareholders is maximized, so the theory provides the conceptual and organizational basis for corporate performance evaluation.

Financial results, customer base growth and development assets such as branches are main performance metrics that are often used. The retention of work then affects the researcher's development, income or client as hypothesis. One challenging issue facing organizations today is employee retention, unlike a quarter of all U.S. workers quit their jobs in 2006. Employment retention, which contributes to the low rate of job turnover, has been related to production globally. In New Zealand, according to [7], worker turnover was related with diminished profitability when the utilization of high-contribution work rehearses was high and efficiency improved when the utilization of these practices was low. By using a retention rate that is the opposite of turnover, the turnover rate can be reinterpreted [8]. Other reports, such as [9], conclude that there is a contradiction between work performance and turnover.

A research in Ghana showed that job retention management should be promoted to develop strategies that will enable improvement of salaries of workers and encourage employees to take e- learning courses and provide fringe benefits such as free medical care, commuting allowance, to help boost work satisfaction, canteen facilities. The investigation would prompt expanded comprehension among directors of maintenance measures and the requirement for more examination in the field [10]. Several studies on work retention have been done in the Kenya region. An analysis [11] on labor turnover in the sugar industry showed that salary is a big salary. cause of employee's turnover and consequently training, promotion, performance appraisal and work condition. Unlike other factors such as recognition, job satisfaction, involvement in decision making and leadership in style didn't have a lot of impact on labor turnover. Contrarily, on the other hand participation in decision making and authority style has a significant impact in execution of laborers and profitability. Moreover, it was perceived absence of representative duty and inspiration are subject to the wide range of various elements causing work turnover yet can significant reasons for worker turnover.

A study of work retention at Kenya Public University [12] found that exploration on worker maintenance are from different countries and are regularly centered around business-situated conditions, and the couple of studies led in Africa in advanced education discuss the problem of brain drain. There are three big SACCOs working in the financial sector in Kericho County. Imarisha SACCO, Ndege Chai SACCO and Kenya Highlands SACCO are among the SACCOs. Imarisha SACCO is a financial services company in Kenya (Imarisha Cooperative Savings & Credit Society Limited). incorporated in 1978. It was called Kipsigis Teacher Saccos and later named Imarisha SACCO. The shares in Imarisha SACCO 's stock are privately held. Nandi hills, Bomet, Kericho, Keringet, Mulot, Awasi, Bureti and Ndanai have the following branches in the SACCO. Kenya Highlands SACCO is another growing one, where tea ranchers and

tea workers are the primary clients. SACCO is developing and branches in Kericho city, Kapsoit, Kabianga and Litein branches are currently opening up.

So long as they have the Kericho branch, Ndenge Chai SACCOs is another growing SACCO. The Three SACCOs are rising and need to move from commercial banks in Kenya to challenge and competition. Although the industry has experienced tremendous growth, different difficulties in SACCOs are likewise found in HR; issues with worker mentalities, nature of administration and money related imperatives are among the difficulties confronted. The profitability of certain specialists is uncertain and companies need to assess their employee retention strategies as a way to achieve their targets in compliance with their expansion strategy. In addition, the organizations have long-serving laborers, some of whom have been with these SACCOs since its beginning, of whom their viability has declined, calling for an analysis and study on the strategies implemented by the SACCOs to ensure that most of its workers have been retained and how these strategies influence organizational efficiency.

II. Statement of the Problem

Productivity has been one of the fundamental problems of most businesses. Organizations have felt the need to take employee turnover into account. Employee turnover also leads to far-reaching effects, and drastic attempts to accomplish organizational goals should be avoided. The company would have a detrimental effect on innovation and efficiency in delivering customer service, triggering service delivery delays. In addition, this turnover will result in decrease services provided to customers and this will affect external and internal customer's satisfaction and the organization profitability. According to [6] direct and indirect costs are associated with turnover due to rates of employees' turnover since low rates are preferable than high rates. This brings lot of concern to the organizations; attracting and retaining qualified talent is one of the biggest challenge facing SACCO and without this actions, organizations are unable to achieve their objectives. There's a lot of cost incurred in losing valuable asset that is employees both in terms of losing productivity, training and hiring a new employee [11 &12]. Throughout recruitment and employment cycle organization should consider the need of employee retention since it's a continuing process and not only retaining them when they are already on board. Resources for recruiting employees are always not available due to tight budgets.

In many SACCOs there is no formal career path for the staff they wish to maintain and they do not grow strengths and abilities, because there are no opportunities to resolve skill shortages, thereby showing daunting and stretching tasks for existing workers. all these result due to unpreparedness for departure of key employees. The talented and skilled would leave the organization because the SACCO lacks succession plan put in place.

Most SACCOS do not focus on motivation and enhancing skills but emphasis on profitability due to limited resources. Hence their salaries are low, lack programs that can enhance work life balance nor promote good organization culture. Their financial plans are tight and staff are extended flimsy, where they become withdrawn and angry prompting untimely turnover. This investigation will be helpful in determining factors influencing decision of employee remaining within the organization or leaving with reasons possible. It seeks to decide the impact of length of administration of a representative on the profitability of an association.

III. Specific Objectives

To examine the influence of career development on organizational productivity of savings and credit co-operative societies in Kericho county

1. Research Question

H₀₁: To what extend does career development influence organizational productivity of SACCOs in Kericho County?

2. Conceptual Framework

IV. Self- Determination Theory

The self-determination rule was developed by [13]. The hypothesis of self-assurance gets the self-governing inspiration predicament. Deliberate consolation assists laborers with favouring preparing and profession development since it gives expanded effectiveness, inventive thoughts (advancements) that give representatives work fulfilment over the long haul. De Cuyper and De Witte [14] contended that the hypothesis of self-inspiration can be isolated into: self-sufficient connections, for example, family, directed intentions, for example, power and instrumental thought processes connected to the accomplishment of particular objectives.

They further claimed that workers should be driven by issues such as career growth and training, work satisfaction and compensation for productivity, managed employee turnover, work satisfaction and customer satisfaction. Due to the fact that employee retention policies actually aid in assessing productivity in any given company, this principle is central to the analysis. Though the theory is valid, the productivity of SACCOs is not shaded by light.

V. Career Development

Managing transitions of learning is crucial and have proved to be contributing to a competitive posterity. When learning is well managed, it influences both the behaviour and the psychology of the learner. This makes the gained knowledge to be motivating and life-changing in long run to the learner. The career development helps improve the quality of decision making by the learner. It guides to the development of good relationships that fulfils the social aspect of the learner. Employers uses the career of the learner as a way to justify the qualification of the learner. However, it cannot be an assurance of the job security but only to feel the employee as a reliable avenue of investment. But the greater look of the career is to enable the learner to go beyond the expectation of the employer to gaining life skills and competencies that make them relevant in the industry at all times [7]

VI. Research Methodology

6.1 Research Design

Study design provides the general blueprint for researchers to direct a study to respond to the research question or test the research hypothesis [15]. The analysis used descriptive research design. In the field analysis, in which variables associated with retention were collected in the field, descriptive research design was important.

6.2 Target Population of the Study

According to their 2016 register chosen from the three significant budgetary SACCOs, Imarisha SACCO Ndege Chai SACCO and Kenya Highlands, this study targeted 600 permanent SACCO employees in Kericho County. A selection was taken from all of the SACCO departments. A representative of 180 staff members, a population structure made with a methodical tendency of fundamentals, personality firms and objects to be analyzed from the population structure, should be selected by a stratified random sampling method. The study looks at the various sub-populations, ensuring that no major population factor is left out during examining, where every populace member has an equivalent likelihood of being the example.

6.3 Research Instrument

Primary data and Secondary data collection methods was used. Ghauri & Grønhaug [16] argued that primary data is fit to collect general information from the sample. The data was collected through self-administered questionnaires. Questionnaires offer reasonably objective data, according to [17], which is relatively easy to analyze..Both structured and unstructured questionnaires was utilized. It enabled information to be retrieved from both population covering a larger

number of responded based its cost and ease of filling the questionnaires. The instrument was tested for validity and reliability before data collection.

6.4 Data Analysis and Presentation

The investigator ensured that the study targets were sufficiently covered by analysis. The study would utilize descriptive statistical strategies to examine information from a group of exploration-based data, for example, how worker maintenance builds representative efficiency. It is centered around the examination of training goals, compensation for career growth and work satisfaction. In presenting the data and explaining the phenomenon under review, graphical tools, tables and maps were used where applicable.

VII. Findings and Discussions

7.1 Response Rate

Responses rate was given by 93 (84.5%) of the total investigated data with a non-response of 17 (15.5 %). This was considered to be high enough to enable the researcher to proceed with the survey. According to [18] a threshold of 80% and above is sufficient enough to continue with the research.

7.2 Devolved Dispute Resolution Mechanisms Descriptive Statistics

The researcher sought to establish the levels of agreement by respondents on the effect of career growth on the competitiveness of the company. The reaction was graded into strong agreement (SA = 5), agreement (A = 4), uncertain (U = 3), disagreement (D = 2) and strong disagreement (SD = 1). The response was further summarized using mean (μ) and SD (σ) descriptive statistics. Table 1 shows the results.

Table 1: Career Development

Statements	Percent					μ	σ
	SA	A	N	D	SD		
The quantity of advancements impact Job maintenance	35.5	51.6	12.9	0.0	0.0	4.226	0.662
Employment maintenance affected by number of courses joined in	0.0	32.3	63.4	4.3	0.0	3.280	0.539
Employment maintenance affected by number of occupation administrators	0.0	29.0	51.6	19.4	0.0	3.097	0.693
Employment maintenance being affected by the quantity of occupation survey and advancements	22.6	53.8	23.7	0.0	0.0	3.989	0.684
The organization have attained competitive posterity by the managing transitions	11.6	39.1	37.9	10.4	2.2	3.418	0.681
Learning is well managed influences both the behaviour and the psychology of the employees	11.3	43.2	30.5	11.4	4.6	3.324	0.691
Career development helps improve the quality of decision making by the learner	13.9	33.3	39.4	7.3	6.1	3.261	0.647
There is development of good relationships that fulfils the social aspect of employees	23.8	46.9	21.3	4.6	3.4	3.792	0.596
Employees gain life skills and competencies that make them relevant in the industry at all times	24.3	39.7	22.9	8.6	4.5	3.461	0.425

According to the study results as indicated in the table above, more than half of the respondents (51.6 %) who participated in the study agreed with the statement that the number of promotions influence job retention with 35.5 % strongly agreeing and 12.9 % stating that they were neutral. However, no proportion disagreed or strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 4.226 and SD of 0.662 respectively. Since the mean value is greater than 3, it means that the amount of short-term courses provided to an employee affects work retention.

The requested that the respondents indicate if employment retention is affected by number of seminars attended. The results indicated that majority of the respondents (63.4 %) were neutral with 32.3 % agreeing. However, 4.3 % disagreed with no proportion strongly disagreeing or strongly agreeing. The measure of central tendency and measures of

variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.280 and a SD of 0.539 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that the number of seminars attended influences work retention.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the number of work supervisors affected job retention. The findings showed that the majority of respondents (51.6%) were neutral, with 29.0% agreeing. However, 19.4 % disagreed with no proportion strongly disagreeing or strongly agreeing. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.097 and a SD of 0.693 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that job retention is influenced by number of job supervisors.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether the amount of job reviews and promotions is affected by job retention. The findings showed that the majority (53.8 percent) of respondents were in agreement with 22.6 % strongly agreeing with 23.7 % stating that they were neutral. However, no proportion disagreed or strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.989 and a SD of 0.684 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that the amount of job reviews and promotions is affected by job retention.

The respondents were requested to show whether the organization have attained competitive posterity by the managing transitions. The results indicated that majority of the respondents (39.1 %) were in agreement with 11.6 % strongly agreeing with 37.9 % stating that they were neutral. However, 10.4 % disagreed and 2.2 % strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.418 and a SD of 0.681 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that the organization have attained competitive posterity by the managing transitions.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether learning is well managed to influence both the behaviour and the psychology of the employees. The results revealed that most of the respondents (43.2 %) were in agreement with 11.3 % strongly agreeing with 30.5 % stating that they were neutral. However, 11.4 % disagreed and 4.6 % strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.324 and a SD of 0.691 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that learning is well managed to influence both the behaviour and the psychology of the employees.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether career development helps improve the quality of decision making by the learner. The results showed that most of the respondents (39.4 %) were neutral with 33.3 % agreeing and 13.9 % strongly agreeing. However, 7.3 % disagreed and 6.1 % strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.261 and a SD of 0.647 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that career development helps improve the quality of decision making by the learner.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether there is development of good relationships that fulfils the social aspect of employees. The results revealed that many of the respondents (46.9 %) agreed with 23.8 % strongly agreeing with 21.3 % stating that they were neutral. However, only 4.6 % disagreed and 3.4 % strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.792 and a SD of 0.596 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that there is development of good relationships that fulfils the social aspect of employees.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether employees gain life skills and competencies that make them relevant in the industry at all times. The results indicated that majority of the respondents (39.7 %) were in agreement with 24.3 % strongly agreeing with 22.9 % stating that they were neutral. However, only 8.6 % disagreed and 4.5 % strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.461 and a SD of 0.425 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that employees gain life skills and competencies that make them relevant in the industry at all times. Career development was highly linked with training but most employees would want to grow in their job place career wise. Illoles (1999) argued that it provides life skills and competence that enable high performance concurring with the findings.

Illoles (1999) states that when learning is well managed, it influences both the behaviour and the psychology of the learner. The career development helps improve the quality of decision making by the learner. It guides to the development of good relationships that fulfils the social aspect of the learner. He states that employers use the career of the learner as a way to justify the qualification of the learner. However, he argues that the greater look of the career is to enable the learner to go beyond the expectation of the employer to gaining life skills and competencies that make them relevant in the industry at all times.

7.3 Organization Productivity

The researcher tried to show the levels of agreement by the respondents with regard to the organization productivity. The response was categorized into strongly agree (SA = 5), agree (A = 4), undecided (U =3), disagree (D = 2) and

strongly disagree (SD = 1). The response was further summarized using descriptive statistics namely mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ). The results are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2: Organizational Productivity

Statements	Percent					μ	σ
	SA	A	N	D	SD		
	9.7	72.0	18.3	0.0	0.0	3.914	0.525
Occupation maintenance affected by number of inner updates	14.0	60.2	25.8	0.0	0.0	3.882	0.623
Occupation maintenance affected by number of remodels	23.7	51.6	24.7	0.0	0.0	3.989	0.699
Holding with representatives outside work.	18.3	63.4	18.3	0.0	0.0	4.000	0.608
Employment maintenance impacted by number of acknowledgments	31.2	38.7	28.0	0.0	0.0	4.012	0.618

Based on the study findings as indicated in Table 4.8, majority of the respondents (72.0 %) who participated in the study agreed with the statement that there are quality services influenced by the number or service provided with 9.7 % strongly agreeing and 18.3 % stating that they were neutral. However, no proportion disagreed or strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.989 and standard deviation of 0.617 respectively. Since the mean value is greater than 3, it implies that quality services Influenced by the amount or the provided service.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether effectiveness is influenced by number of jobs done. The results revealed that majority of the respondents (51.6 %) who participated agreed with the statement effectiveness is influenced by number of jobs done with 23.7 % strongly agreeing and 24.7 % stating that they were neutral. However, no proportion disagreed or strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 3.989 and a standard deviation of 0.699 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that there is effectiveness is influenced by number of jobs done.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether effectiveness is influenced by number of customers served. The results indicated that majority of the respondents (63.4 %) who participated agreed with the statement effectiveness is influenced by number of customers served with 18.3 % strongly agreeing and 18.3 % stating that they were neutral. However, no proportion disagreed or strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 4.000 and a standard deviation of 0.608 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that there is effectiveness is influenced by number of customers served.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether effectiveness is influenced by number of customers served. The results indicated that majority of the respondents (38.7 %) who participated agreed with the statement effectiveness is influenced by number of customers served with 31.2 % strongly agreeing and 28.0 % stating that they were neutral. However, no proportion disagreed or strongly disagreed. The measure of central tendency and measures of variation were used to summarize the findings yielding a mean score of 4.012 and a standard deviation of 0.618 respectively. Since the mean response was greater than 3, it is clear that there is effectiveness is influenced by number of customers served. Organization productivity has been determined by quality, customer delivery, customer share, effectiveness and effectiveness (mean of 4.012). Its variance on organization productivity was low (standard deviation of 0.618).

7.4 Correlation Analysis

The researcher conducted Karl Pearson correlation tests in testing the relationship between career development on organization productivity. The results are presented in correlation matrix in Table 3. Decision was based on 5% levels of significance.

Table 3: Correlations Matrix

		Career Development
	Pearson Correlation	.551**
Organization Productivity	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	93

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

On testing the relationship between career development and organization productivity yielded correlation coefficient $r=0.551$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$. This implies that there is a strong positive relationship between career development and organization productivity that is significant at 5% levels of significant.

VIII. Conclusions and Recommendations

Career development was significant and positive on productivity which was contributed by number of promotion, seminars, job supervisors and job review. It is important for organization to improve the environment and ensure that they maintain good working environment. Also recognition and promotion which are part of career development strategies are crucial in organization performance.

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